

Accelerating LLM-Based Algorithm Evolution for the 3D Container Loading Problem: Supplementary Material

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S1 Limitations

While our framework demonstrates strong performance on the Single Container Loading Problem, there are several limitations that define the scope of this study and point toward future work. First, our experiments focused on a standard set of geometric constraints. While these are representative of the single container loading domain, real-world logistics often involve additional complexities, such as multi-drop (LIFO) sequencing, weight distribution for vehicle balance, and varied item fragility requirements. Our current study did not evaluate how well the discovered heuristics adapt to these more specialized constraints.

Second, the discovery process in this work is conducted within a fixed constructive framework (Greedy). While this ensures physical feasibility and reduces the search space for the LLM, it limits the discovery to selection-based logic. The discovery of entirely new algorithmic structures, such as tree search strategies or meta-heuristic frameworks, was beyond the scope of this investigation.

Finally, our evaluation was conducted on classical BR datasets. While these are the academic standard for benchmarking, exploring the performance of LLM-discovered heuristics on large-scale, industrial datasets with thousands of items per container remains a subject for future investigation.

S2 Details of Mutator Ablation

We evaluated multiple mutation strategies on a benchmark population of 30 representative code samples drawn from an Evolution of Heuristics (EoH) process. These samples were selected from 6,000 unique candidates generated across three independent EoH runs. After normalizing the code by removing comments and non-essential whitespace, each sample was embedded into a 4096-dimensional space using the qwen3-embedding-8b model. We applied K-means clustering to obtain 30 clusters and selected the highest-fitness individual from each cluster as a parent seed.

S3 Experimental Details

We conducted all experiments under a fixed mutation budget of 4,000 mutations. Each configuration was executed independently six times to ensure statistical reliability. The population size was fixed at $N = 10$ across all experiments. We set the SMAC hyperparameter optimization to tune 5 parameters with 10 trials each, and the

pruning operator was configured to evaluate 5 candidate ablations per mutation. The complexity threshold was set to $\tau = 2$ for all experiments unless otherwise specified.

The evolutionary process was executed in a fully asynchronous manner: ($N = 10$) persistent workers repeatedly retrieved parent solutions from the population, applied mutation, inserted the resulting offspring back into the population, and then sampled the next mutation, following the architecture described in [4]. We compared our approach against Vanilla EoH, baseline heuristics (BSG, G2LA), and the current state-of-the-art method (VCS).

After evolution, each heuristic was evaluated on a test set consisting of 90 instances for each of the 8 BR benchmarks, for a total of 720 test instances. We report both the mean and standard deviation across the six independent runs, as well as the single best-performing code for each configuration.

S4 Algorithm concept

We analyze the best heuristic discovered by our framework and abstract its core logic against the principles used in the VCS human-designed framework. We identify four geometric concepts shared between both heuristics, summarized as follows:

1. Block Volume

VCS Logic: Prioritizes blocks with larger physical volume.

LLM Evolutionary Logic: Inherited from the seed program.

2. Wasted Volume

VCS Logic: Solves three 1D knapsack problems to estimate if remaining space is usable.

LLM Evolutionary Logic:

- **Look-ahead:** Tests whether residual spaces meet the minimum dimensions of available blocks.
- **Space Utilization:** Penalizes wasted volume by the ratio of unused space after placement to usable space before placement.
- **Hardcoded Control:** Discourages placements that lead to residual spaces with dimensions below a minimum usable threshold (MIN_FRAGMENT_DIM).

3. Surface Contact

VCS Logic: Computes the proportion of block surface area in contact with container walls and other blocks; higher

contact implies fewer exposed edges.

LLM Evolutionary Logic:

- **Z-Axis Support:** Restricts placements to those supported from below.
- **Wall Proximity:** Uses Manhattan distance to reward corner and wall adjacency.

4. Item Count

VCS Logic: Favors blocks composed of fewer items.

LLM Evolutionary Logic: Inherited from the seed program.

S5 Details of Benchmark Heuristics

The baselines considered in our evaluation are summarized as follows:

- (1) **VCS Score[1]:** Evaluates box selection using a comprehensive scoring function that accounts for remaining space, contact surface area, volume, and item count [1]. For space selection, it prioritizes the Manhattan distance from the origin and the volume of available space.
- (2) **BCS Score[2]:** Employs a scoring function introduced by Araya and Riff [2]. For box selection, it formulates a knapsack problem to perform a one-step look-ahead evaluation of the remaining space. For space selection, it relies primarily on the Manhattan distance from the origin.
- (3) **G2LA Score[5]:** Utilizes the *Greedy with 2-Step Look-Ahead* heuristic proposed by Zhu et al. [5]. This method prioritizes spaces based on their Manhattan distance from the origin and selects blocks that maximize volume utilization while minimizing projected waste through a two-step look-ahead trimming strategy.

S6 Experimental Details for Ablation Study

S6.1 Impact of Complexity on Generalization

Our complexity-aware regularization mechanism aims to mitigate overfitting by constraining heuristic complexity, which we study by varying the complexity threshold ($\tau \in 2, 3, 5$) and conducting a post-hoc regularization analysis. To assess the impact of complexity, We first analyze the evolutionary trajectory of training fitness over time to evaluate convergence speed and stability, and second perform a post-hoc evaluation among all the heuristic populations generated during the evolutionary search. We regularize the fitness function to include a complexity penalty like in Hottung et al. [3], defined as the code length (in lines) of the heuristic. We plot the test performance against regularized strength, using the proxy score: train fitness – $\lambda \times$ code length.

S6.2 Efficiency of Search Operators

We compare different combinations of search operators to study their efficiency in discovering high-quality heuristics. Specifically, we evaluate the following configurations: We keep the tuning and pruning operators, and vary the structural mutation operators as follows:

- **Extend Only:** Use only the Extend operator for structural mutations.
- **EoH Mutators:** Use the original EoH M1, E1, and E2 operators for structural mutations.

- **Extend + Crossover:** Combine the Extend operator with the biased Components crossover operator for structural mutations inspired by Hottung et al. [3].

References

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